

PHOTONITRIFICATION AND NITROGEN LOSS FROM SOLUTIONS OF DIFFERENT AMMONIUM SALTS

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Nitrification of several ammonium salts has been carried out in sunlight and in dark. The effect of sunlight has been found in all cases to accelerate nitrification.

The process of nitrification is always associated with the loss of nitrogen through the intermediate formation of ammonium nitrite.

In publications from this laboratory, it has been emphasised that light plays an important rôle in many oxidation reactions and the process of ammonification, nitrification and loss of nitrogen are markedly accelerated by light absorption.

We have carried on further experiments on nitrification of numerous ammonium salt solutions in sunlight and in the dark and our results are recorded in this paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Different ammonium salt solutions (100 c.c. each) were taken in conical glass flasks. In each case the nitrogen content at the beginning of the experiments was kept at 0.4, 0.2, 0.1 and 0.05 g. nitrogen per 100 c.c. of solution. Precipitated calcium carbonate (1 g.) was added to each flask to serve as a surface. Each solution was taken in two sets of flasks, one set was exposed to sunlight and the other was kept covered with black cloth to exclude light radiations by the side of the exposed sets.

After an exposure of five to six weeks the contents of the flasks were analysed for ammoniacal nitrogen left unoxidised and the nitric nitrogen formed due to the oxidation of ammonium salts by the usual methods.

The experimental results are recorded below.

TABLE I

I. Ammonium persulphate solutions exposed from 10-12-1946 to 10-1-47. (Mean temp. = 32°).

No.	Original N per 100 c.c. soln.	NH ₃ -N left un- oxidised in		Nitric N formed in		Loss of N in	
		Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.
1	0.40 g.	0.3681 g.	0.3814 g.	0.0241 g.	0.0179 g.	2.0%	0.3%
2	0.20	0.1231	0.1318	0.0144	0.0099	31.4	29.4
3	0.10	0.0714	0.0779	0.0048	0.0018	23.8	20.3
4	0.05	0.0298	0.0323	0.0021	0.0012	36.2	33.0

II. Ammonium sulphate solutions exposed from 21-1-47 to 7-3-47. (Mean temp. = 35.5°).

No.	Original N per 100 c.c. soln.	NH ₃ -N left un- oxidised in		Nitric N formed in		Loss of N in	
		Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.
1	0.40 g.	0.1645 g.	0.2729 g.	0.0108 g.	0.0040 g.	56.0%	37%
2	0.20	0.0658	0.0949	0.0047	0.0005	65.0	52.0
3	0.10	0.0140	0.0406	0.0024	0.0002	83.0	58.8
4	0.05	0.0130	0.0212	0.0016	0.0000	81.0	58.0

TABLE I (contd.)

III. Ammonium phosphate solutions exposed from 21-1-47 to 7-3-47. (Mean temp. = 35.5°).							
No.	Original N per 100 c.c. soln.	NH ₃ -N left un-oxidised in		Nitric-N formed in		Loss of N in	
		Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.
1	0.40 g.	0.1780 g.	0.2030 g.	0.0072 g.	0.0034 g.	53.7%	48.4%
2	0.20	0.0260	0.0284	0.0030	0.0010	88.5	85.0
3	0.10	0.0005	0.0008	0.0008	0.0001	98.7	99.1
4	0.05	0.000	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000	100.0	99.8
IV. Ammonium perchlorate solutions exposed from 21-7-47 to 27-9-47. (Mean temp. = 35.5°).							
1	0.40 g.	0.2299 g.	0.2811 g.	0.0027 g.	0.0016 g.	41.8%	29.3%
2	0.20	0.0925	0.1132	0.0014	0.0010	53.0	42.9
3	0.10	0.0324	0.0413	0.0009	0.0005	66.7	58.2
4	0.05	0.0116	0.0160	0.0005	0.0001	75.8	67.9
V. Ammonium dichromate solutions exposed from 21-7-47 to 27-9-47. (Mean temp. = 35.5°).							
1	0.40 g.	0.3227 g.	0.3600 g.	0.0028 g.	0.0020 g.	18.6%	9.5%
2	0.20	0.1146	0.1531	0.0016	0.0012	41.9	22.8
3	0.10	0.0497	0.0579	0.0008	0.0006	49.5	42.0
4	0.05	0.0152	0.0258	0.0006	0.0004	68.4	47.6
VI. Ammonium nitrate solutions exposed from 21-7-47 to 27-9-47. (Mean temp. = 35.5°).							
1	0.80 g.	0.2388 g.	0.2785 g.	0.3727 g.	0.3765 g.	23.5%	18.5%
2	0.40	0.0801	0.1101	0.1872	0.1904	33.2	24.8
3	0.20	0.0265	0.0366	0.0896	0.0906	41.9	36.4
4	0.10	0.0105	0.0150	0.0450	0.0464	44.5	38.6

The above experimental results with all ammonium salts excepting ammonium nitrate show that a considerable amount of the ammonium salt is oxidised and an appreciable amount of nitric nitrogen is formed in every case. The effect of sunlight is found to be very marked in all the cases, the amount of ammonium salts oxidised being always greater in the salts exposed to sunlight than those kept in the dark. Also, the amount of nitric nitrogen formed in the exposed flasks is much greater than that formed in the covered ones.

If the nitrification of ammonium salts were only of bacterial origin, as it is generally believed, and not a photochemical and surface oxidation reaction, the ammonium salts in the covered sets should have also undergone oxidation at least to the same extent as the exposed ones. On the other hand, our results definitely go to show that, whilst large amounts of ammonium salts are oxidised to nitrite and nitrate in presence of light, much less oxidation and nitrate formation of ammonium salts take place in the covered vessels. It appears therefore that nitrification of ammonium salts is to a large extent an induced surface oxidation reaction aided by light radiations.

Another important point brought out by these results is that the process of nitrification is always associated with nitrogen loss. In the case of loss also, the factor of light radiations plays an important part; the loss in the exposed sets is found to be always greater than the loss in the covered sets.

The loss of nitrogen has been explained by us from the view point that during nitrification, ammonium nitrite is produced as an intermediate product and this readily decomposes into water and nitrogen gas which escapes and causes the loss.

As the oxidation of ammonium salts is always more pronounced in light than in the dark, there is always the possibility of greater amounts of ammonium nitrite formation in the sets exposed to light than in the dark and hence there is always more nitrogen loss found in the exposed sets than in the covered ones.

It is to be seen from the results that the greater the initial nitrogen content, the greater is the loss of nitrogen, though the percentage loss increases with dilution. Though at first consideration the greater percentage loss with dilution seems unexpected, but a closer analysis of these results reveals the marked influence of surface on the reaction. The amount of calcium carbonate (used as surface) in all the concentrations of the solution is the same and the volume of the solution is also the same; hence the possibility of an ammonium ion coming in contact with the active centres of the surface is increased on increasing the dilution of the ammonium salt. When the concentration of the ammonium ions is increased, the total number of ions coming in contact with the active centres is also increased, but the percentage of the ions coming in contact with surface is decreased. On the other hand, with increase in dilution, the total number of ions coming in contact with the surface, though decreased, yet the percentage of ions coming in contact with the active spots of the surface is increased, and as a result of this the percentage loss of nitrogen is found to be more in the lower concentrations of the ammonium salt solutions.

Moreover, there is a slight loss of ammonia gas in these experiments, as calcium carbonate is slightly alkaline.

The experimental results show clearly that the loss is maximum with ammonium phosphate. This is due to the fact that there is a double decomposition between calcium carbonate and ammonium phosphate with the formation of calcium phosphate and ammonium carbonate, which slowly decomposes into carbon dioxide and ammonia.

The loss with other substances is in the following decreasing order: ammonium phosphate, ammonium sulphate, ammonium perchlorate, ammonium dichromate, ammonium nitrate and ammonium persulphate.

It appears that with ammonium persulphate the loss of nitrogen is the least. With ammonium dichromate and nitrate, though the loss is greater than with ammonium persulphate, yet, is less than with other ammonium salts. These results showing different losses with different ammonium salts, specially when the acid ion is an oxidising one, is of considerable interest. Moreover, the results with ammonium nitrate show that the nitric nitrogen in the system is appreciably less after the exposure than the original amount of nitric ion introduced. This is due to the fact that the free ammonium hydroxide obtained by the action of calcium carbonate and ammonium nitrate is partially lost by escape of free ammonia gas and another part of the ammonium

hydroxide reacts with the nitrate ion forming nitrite ion which in combination with ammonium ion decomposes as nitrogen gas. This reduction of nitrate ion to nitrite appears to be more prominent in light than in the dark and hence the nitric nitrogen present in the system after exposure is always appreciably less than in the system kept in the dark.

It is generally believed that ammonium persulphate decomposes in the following manner in aqueous solutions :

It appears that in this process small amounts of nitrous acid is also formed and this decomposes according to the equation,

With ammonium persulphate the loss of nitrogen is the least because in presence of acids, ammonium nitrite cannot exist but it forms nitrous acid. Moreover, the nitric nitrogen with ammonium persulphate is much higher than with other ammonium salts (24.1 mg. in the highest concentration in light while 10.8 mg. under similar conditions in ammonium sulphate and 7.2 mg. in ammonium phosphate). This is due to the fact that the ammonium ion in this case is oxidised chiefly by the persulphate ion into nitric acid, whilst with the other ammonium salts the oxidation is mainly caused by the dissolved oxygen and the process is much slower.

C O N C L U S I O N

The results show that ammonium salts are nitrified on exposure to light.

The amount of salt oxidised is greater in light than in the dark, also the amount of nitrate formed is much more in exposed sets than in the covered ones.

During nitrification a considerable amount of nitrogen is lost as gaseous nitrogen due to decomposition of the intermediate compound, ammonium nitrite, formed during the reaction.

Light seems to have an important effect on the amount of nitrogen loss, the loss being always greater in sunlight than in the dark.

Greater the initial nitrogen, the greater is the loss, though the percentage loss increases with decreasing concentration of ammonium salts.

Nitrification seems to be partly surface oxidation reaction catalysed by sunlight.

Loss of nitrogen is maximum with ammonium phosphate and minimum with ammonium persulphate.

With ammonium nitrate, the nitrate content after exposure is less in the exposed vessels than the original concentration of nitrate ion. This is due to the reaction between ammonia and nitrate ion and the formation of ammonium nitrite.